

that of the checks. The results of the present experiment suggest that improvement of parental lines is needed for F₁ hybrids to show further superiority over checks. □

Yield depression in F₂ hybrids of rice
Oryza sativa L.

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We evaluated four F₂ rice hybrids and their corresponding F₁ parents with IR54, a recommended pureline variety, as check in a replicated yield trial in 1983 dry season at IIRRI. Twenty-one-day-old seedlings were transplanted at 20- × 20-cm spacing and one seedling per hill, in 5.0- × 3.4-m plots, NPK was applied at 120-50-30 kg/ha.

The F₁ hybrids and IR54 flowered relatively earlier and were more uniform in flowering and plant height than the F₂.

Yield and yield depression in F₂ rice hybrids and the corresponding F₁ hybrids.

Hybrid, check	Yield (t/ha)		Yield depression ^a (%) in F ₂
	F ₁ hybrid	F ₂ hybrid	
IET3257/IR2797-105-2-2-3	8.3	6.6	-21**
IET3257/IR54	8.3	6.8	-19**
IR11248-242-3-2/IR15324-117-3-2	7.7	6.6	-14**
IR1124&242-3-2/IR19672-19-3-3-1	8.2	6.8	-18**
IR54 (check)	6.7		

^a ** = significant at 1% level.

Flowering took about 15 d between 99 and 114 d after sowing in IET3257/IR2797 and 12 d for the 3 other F₂ hybrids. Uneven F₂ plant height, flowering, and maturity were due to segregation of genes for those traits.

Grain yield was determined from 5 m². Because of staggered F₂ maturity, plants were harvested on two dates. Grain yield was adjusted to 14% moisture, and reported in t/ha. Yield depression in F₂ was computed as (F₂ - F₁) ÷ F₁ and expressed as a percentage. Statistical significance of the difference was tested using LSD.

Yield depression (see table) in F₂ ranged from 14 to 21% and was significant in all the hybrids. However, the F₂ yields were comparable with those of IR54. The highest yield depression in F₂ was observed in the combination IET3257/IR2797. The same combination had also expressed the highest yield heterosis in F₁. Therefore, to exploit the yield advantage of F₁ rice hybrids, it would be necessary to sow fresh F₁ seed every year. Sowing F₂ seed (harvest made from F₁ rice hybrid) would significantly reduce yield. □

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

TISSUE CULTURE

Response of rice anthers to callus induction and plant regeneration

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Anther culture can speed genetic improvement of crops by increasing selection efficiency within a short time. We studied the response of anthers to culture medium.

Cold shocked anthers of 40 boro varieties, breeding lines, and F₂ plants were cultured in N6 (for japonica) and modified H5 and SK-8 (for indica and indica/japonica) media at early to mid-uninucleate stage of microspore development. Of the 18 lines that produced calli, 2 were japonicas, 1 was indica/japonica, and 15 were indicas. Anther

Rice anther variability in inducing callus and plant differentiation, Dhaka, Bangladesh.

Variety or line	Type	Anthers inoculated (no.)	Induction		Differentiation ^a (%)		
			No.	%	Roots only	Albino plants	Green plants
Zhing hua-2	japonica	270	60	22	50	18	0
Zhing hua-5	japonica	600	222	37	30	37	25
BG96-3/J2	indica	311	23	7	33	33	17
BR161-2B-58	indica	262	6	2	60	0	0
Guichao No. 2	indica	368	2	0	100	0	0
Habiganj Boro-VI	indica	155	39	25	50	30	0
Habiganj Boro VIII	indica	162	56	35	45	10	0
IR40	indica	330	11	3	57	14	0
IR19660-11	indica	215	3	1	33	0	0
IR19660-311	indica	404	68	13	70	15	5
IR19090-24-5-3-1-1	indica	230	1	0	100	0	0
Pajam	indica/japonica	1825	82	4	48	27	11
Zenith	indica	230	3	1	67	0	0
BR4228 (F ₂)	indica	840	54	6	37	35	10
BR4229 (F ₂)	indica	295	8	3	60	40	0
BR4249 (F ₂)	indica	480	15	3	50	20	0
BR4251 (F ₂)	indica	455	3	1	100	0	0
BR4252 (F ₂)	indica	575	12	2	50	20	0
Total (induction)		8007	668	8.34	-	-	-
Weighted av (differentiation) ^a		-	-	-	48.3	23.1	7.7

^a Based on number of calli transferred for differentiation.

response ranged from 0.4 to 37.0%. Zhing hua #5 and Habiganj Boro VIII had the best response (see table).

Two wk after induction, the anther calli were transferred to MS regeneration

medium supplemented with 0.5 mg IAA/litre and 1.0 mg kinetin/litre. The percentage of root development was 30.8 to 100%. Albinism was higher than green plant regeneration (see table).

High callusing ability of varieties indicates their potential to be cultured in a nutrient medium, which indicates the need for screening rice germplasm for callusing ability. □

Culture conditions and callus-forming ability of rice anthers

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More efficient anther culture techniques, especially for indica rices, are needed to speed varietal development through anther culture.

The callusing ability (CA) of anthers of 3 indica and indica/japonica varieties, and 4 F₂ lines in 5 different media ranged from 0 to 25.0% (Table 1). IR19660-311 and Pajam responded to five media and an F₂ line of BR7/Basmati 370 responded to two. The CA of the anthers of these varieties or lines was different in different media, but N6, a medium developed in China for japonica varieties, did not perform as well as the other media, especially for the pure indicas. The CA of the anthers of these varieties or lines differed significantly when cultured in the five media, indicating the existence of genotypic variability among them (Table 1).

CA of Pajam anthers ranged from 0.0 to 6.9 under light (mean 2.2%) and 4.0 to 9.0% in darkness (mean 7.0%) (Table 2). The difference between these two means was significant, indicating that the CA may be increased by manipulating incubation conditions. Similarly, the differentiation of calli into green plants was comparatively higher with anthers obtained from modified H5 medium and dark incubation. However, regeneration into albino plants was more frequent than into green plants (Table 2). □

Table 1. Response of anthers of indica, indica/japonica varieties, and F₂ lines to callus induction in different media, Dhaka, Bangladesh.

Varieties and lines	Callus-forming ability ^a (%) in the media					Mean ^b
	N6	Modified N6	H5	Modified H5	SK-8	
BG96-3/J2	0.0	10.0	7.1	11.1	12.5	8.1 b
IR19660-311	6.9	12.3	22.7	25.0	14.1	16.2 a
Pajam	3.2	2.6	3.8	8.3	5.7	4.7 bcd
IR3249-19-1-3/Hbj. Boro	0.0	5.0	7.0	12.2	5.7	6.1 bc
IV (F ₂)						
IR2003-P3-3-1-2/Amboro	0.0	1.3	1.0	2.4	5.3	3.2 ale
II (F ₂)						
BR7/Baimati 370 (F ₂)	0.0	0.0	0.0	2.1	1.2	0.7 e
Dymisia/IR424-2-1-57414 (F ₂)	0.0	1.3	3.2	3.8	1.8	2.0 de
Mean	0.5	4.4 a	3.7 a	6.8 a	5.4 a	—

^a Callus-forming ability (%) = $\frac{\text{no. of anthers producing callus}}{\text{no. of anthers inoculated}} \times 100$.

^b Means followed by different letters are significantly different at P0.05 level.

Table 2. Effect of media and incubation condition on callus-forming ability and differentiation of Pajam, Dhaka, Bangladesh.

Medium	Incubation ^a condition	Anthers inoculated (no.)	Callus produced		Differentiation ^b (%)		
			No.	%	Roots only	Albino plants	Green plants
N6	Light	180	3	1.7	66.7	33.3	—
	Dark	160	8	5.0	60.0	20.0	—
Modified N6	Light	110	0	0.0	—	—	—
	Dark	200	8	4.0	33.3	33.3	—
H5	Light	150	1	0.7	100.0	—	—
	Dark	115	9	7.8	66.7	22.2	11.1
Modified H5	Light	145	10	6.9	66.7	16.7	16.7
	Dark	290	26	9.0	56.7	13.3	20.2
SK-8	Light	175	3	1.7	33.3	33.3	—
	Dark	300	24	8.0	50.0	21.4	7.1
Total	Light	760	17	2.2 b	61.5	23.1	7.7
	Dark	1065	75	7.0 a ^c	51.0	20.4	10.2

^a Light = inoculated anthers were incubated under light for 13 h/d (about 2500 lux) at 26±1 °C. Dark = inoculated anthers were initially incubated in darkness for 15 d and then under light for 13 h/d at 26±1°C for the rest of the period. ^b Calculated on the basis of number of calli transferred for differentiation in M.S. medium supplemented with 0.5 mg IAA and 1.0 mg kinetin/litre. ^c Significantly different at P0.05 level.

The International Rice Research Newsletter (IRRN) invites all scientists to contribute concise summaries of significant rice research for publication. Contributions should be limited to one or two pages and no more than two short tables, figures, or photographs. Contributions are subject to editing and abridgment to meet space limitations. Authors will be identified by name, title, and research organization.